

Research Article

To Formulate and Evaluate of Rivaroxaban Immediate Release Tablets Using Super Disintegrants and Surfactant

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The present study aimed to formulate and evaluate immediate release tablets of rivaroxaban using superdisintegrants and a surfactant to enhance dissolution and oral bioavailability. Rivaroxaban, a poorly water-soluble anticoagulant, exhibits dissolution-limited absorption, necessitating formulation strategies to improve its release profile. Immediate release tablets were prepared by direct compression employing different concentrations of superdisintegrants such as croscarmellose sodium, sodium starch glycolate, and crospovidone, along with a suitable surfactant to improve wettability and drug dispersion. The prepared formulations were evaluated for pre-compression parameters including angle of repose, bulk density, tapped density, Carr's index, and Hausner's ratio, which indicated satisfactory flow properties. Post-compression evaluation involved assessment of tablet hardness, thickness, friability, weight variation, drug content uniformity, disintegration time, and in vitro dissolution studies. The optimized formulation demonstrated acceptable physicochemical properties, rapid disintegration, and significantly enhanced drug release compared to formulations without surfactant. In vitro dissolution results showed compliance with pharmacopeial requirements for immediate release dosage forms. The study concludes that the combined use of superdisintegrants and surfactant is an effective approach for developing immediate release rivaroxaban tablets with improved dissolution characteristics, potentially leading to better therapeutic performance.

Keywords: rivaroxaban, as croscarmellose sodium, sodium starch glycolate, and crospovidone, poorly water-soluble anticoagulant, surfactant.

INTRODUCTION

Drug delivery system (DDS) is a strategic tool for expanding markets, extending product life cycles and generating opportunities. Tablet is a solid pharmaceutical dosage form containing drug substances with or without suitable diluent and prepared by compression or molding method. Rivaroxaban is anticoagulant. It inhibits the blood coagulation. It is used to treat and prevent deep vein thrombosis (DVT), which can lead to blood clots in the lungs (pulmonary embolism). Rivaroxaban is a direct factor Xa inhibitor. It works by blocking the process of formation of blood clots².

1.1 Oral Drug Delivery³

The oral route is one of the most desirable routes for the systemic drug delivery due to its ease of ingestion, simple, safest, convenient, non-invasive, versatility and most importantly, patient compliance. Solid oral delivery systems are cheaply manufactured because they don't require sterile conditions. Although, increased focus and interest generated in the area of controlled release and targeted drug delivery system in recent years, tablet dosage forms that are intended to be swallowed whole, disintegrate, and release their medicament fast and furiously in the gastrointestinal tract⁴.

1.2 Tablets⁵

Tablets is a solid preparation which contains a single dose of one or more active ingredients and obtained by compressing uniform volumes of particles. Some

are dissolved or dispersed in water before being administered and some are retained in the mouth, where the active ingredient “liberated”⁵. Tablets remain popular as a dosage form because of the advantages like afforded both to the manufacturer (e.g., simplicity and economy of preparation, stability and convenience in packing, shipping and dispensing) and the patient (e.g., accuracy of dosage, compactness, portability, blandness of taste and ease of administration)⁶. Tablets may differ greatly in size and weight depending on the amount of drug substance present and the intended method of

administration. Although tablets are more frequently discoid in shape, they also may be round, oval, oblong, cylindrical or triangular. They may have lines or break-marks and may bear a symbol or other markings. Tablets may be coated or non-coated⁷.

1.2.1 Mechanism of Tablet Disintegration^{8,9}:

The mechanism by which the tablets are broken into small pieces and then produce a homogeneous suspension is based on the following steps: -

Figure 1: Mechanism of Tablet Disintegration

1.2.2 Super Disintegrants in Immediate Release Tablets^{10,11}

A disintegrant is an excipient which is added to a tablet or capsule blend to aid in the breakup of the compacted mass when it is put into a fluid environment. This is especially important for immediate release products where rapid release of drug substance is required.

2. Drug Profile and Excipient Profile

2.1 Drug Profile

Rivaroxaban

Rivaroxaban is an anticoagulant and the first orally active direct factor Xa inhibitor. Unlike warfarin, routine lab monitoring is not necessary. However, there is no antidote available in the event of a major bleed. Only the 10 mg tablet can be taken without regard to food. The 15 mg and 20 mg tablet should be taken with food. FDA approved on July 1, 2011. Specifically, it is used to treat deep vein thrombosis and pulmonary emboli and prevent blood clots in atrial fibrillation and following hip or knee surgery. Rivaroxaban was patented in 2007 and approved for medical use in the United States in 2011. In the United States, it will not be available as a generic medication until 2024.

IUPAC Name:

5-chloro-N - ((5 S) -2-oxo-3- [4- (3-oxo-4-morpholinyl) phenyl] -1,3-oxazolidin 5-yl) - methyl) -2-thiophenecarboxamide.

CAS No.: 366789-02-8.

Molecular Weight: 435.9 g/mol. **Molecular Formula:** C₁₉H₁₈ClN₃O₅S **Log P value:** 1.5

Structural Formula:

Figure 6: Structure of Rivaroxaban

Properties:

Description: Rivaroxaban is a pure (S)-enantiomer. It is an odourless, non-hygroscopic, white to yellowish powder.

Solubility:

Rivaroxaban is only slightly soluble in organic solvents (e.g., acetone, polyethylene glycol 400) and is practically insoluble in water and aqueous media. DMSO 20 mg/mL; Water <1 mg/mL

Melting Point: 227-230°C.

Storage: Store in a well-closed container.

Indication:

Rivaroxaban is indicated for the prevention of venous thromboembolic events (VTE) in patients who have undergone total hips replacements and total knee replacement surgery; prevention of stroke and systemic embolism in patients with nonvalvular atrial fibrillation; treatment of deep vein thrombosis (DVT) and pulmonary embolism (PE); to reduce risk of recurrent DVT and/or PE. Rivaroxaban is also indicated, in combination with aspirin, for reducing the risk of major cardiovascular events in patients with chronic coronary artery disease or peripheral artery disease. Due to a lack of safety studies, it is not recommended for use in those under 18 years old. Its

use is also not recommended in those with severe renal impairment

Dosage and Administration Rivaroxaban

2.5 mg, 10 mg, 15 mg, 20 mg available as tablets. Indicated for reduction in risk of recurrence of DVT and/or PE in patients at continued risk for recurrent DVT and/or PE after completion of initial treatment lasting at least 6 months 10 mg PO qDay, after at least 6 months of standard anticoagulant treatment

Reduction of Risk of Major Cardiovascular Events

In combination with aspirin, is indicated to reduce the risk of major cardiovascular events (cardiovascular [CV] death, myocardial infarction [MI] and stroke) in patients with chronic coronary artery disease (CAD) or peripheral artery disease (PAD).

2.1.1 Pharmacokinetics:

2.1.1.1 Absorption: [Oral administration]

Rivaroxaban is rapidly absorbed and reaches peak plasma concentration in 2-4 hours. Bioavailability of the 10 mg dose is >80%. However, the 15-20 mg dose have a lower bioavailability if taken in the fasted state and consequently should be taken with food.

2.1.1.2 Distribution:

- The steady state Vd is 50 L
- Plasma protein binding is about 92% to 95%

2.1.1.3 Metabolism:

Approximately two-thirds of the dose is metabolized. It is metabolized by CYP3A4, CYP3A5, CYP2J2 and CYP independent mechanisms²⁹.

2.1.1.4 Excretion:

Approximately two-thirds of rivaroxaban is excreted into urine (via active tubular secretion in which approximately 36% as unchanged drug and 30% as inactive metabolism). The remaining third of the administered dose is excreted via faeces in which 7% is in the form of unchanged drug and 21% as inactive metabolites. The terminal half-life is 5-9 hours in adults and 11-13 hours in the elderly. Systemic

clearance is approximately 10 L/h, so rivaroxaban is considered a drug with low clearance. Renal clearance is ~3-4 L/h. 6.4.

2.1.2. Pharmacodynamics Mechanism of Action:

Rivaroxaban competitively inhibits free and clot bound factor Xa. Factor Xa is needed to activate prothrombin (factor II) to thrombin (factor IIa).

Thrombin is a serine protease that is required to activate fibrinogen to fibrin, which is the loose meshwork that completes the clotting process. Since one molecule of factor Xa can generate more than 1000 molecules of thrombin, selective inhibitors of factor Xa are profoundly useful in terminating the amplification of thrombin generation. The action of rivaroxaban is irreversible^{30,31,32}.

Figure 7: Mechanism of action of Rivaroxaban

3. Experimental Work

3.1. Procurement of API and Characterization

Rivaroxaban is official drug in United States Pharmacopoeia. API was procured from Lupin Pharmaceuticals limited, Mumbai as a gift sample. Before usage of the drug, identification of drug was done using various pharmacopeial parameters as per USP.

- **Organolectic Properties**

The drug sample was analysed for physical appearance, colour and odour.

- **Melting Point Determination**

The melting point of rivaroxaban was recorded by capillary method using melting point apparatus and was compared with literature reported data.

- **UV Visible Spectroscopy UV Spectrum (λ_{max})**

A solution of rivaroxaban 10 ppm was prepared in acetate buffer and the maximum absorption wavelength was noted.

Construction of Calibration Curve of Rivaroxaban:

Preparation of Standard Stock Solution:

1000 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of rivaroxaban solution was prepared by dissolving 100 mg of rivaroxaban in few ml of pH 4.5 acetate buffer and the volume made upto 100 ml. From above solution, 10 ml solution was pipette out and dilute upto 100 ml with acetate buffer. Resulted solution was 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. The solution was further diluted to get various working solution.

Preparation of standard dilutions:

For linearity study, dilutions were made for rivaroxaban in the concentration range of 2, 4, 6, 8, 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ by diluting the stock solution with acetate buffer. The calibration curve was established at 248 nm by plotting the graph between concentration verses absorbance. graph was plotted and linear equation and regression analysis (r^2) was noted in Figure 14 and 15.

- **Saturation Solubility Studies**

The solubility of rivaroxaban was determined in various solvents like hydrochloric acid (pH 1.2), phosphate buffer (pH 6.8) and acetate buffer (pH 4.6 with 0.4% SLS). The solvents were taken in 5 mL glass vial. An excess amount of drug was added in each vial and closed with stopper. These glass vials were attached in an orbital shaking water bath. The shaking was carried out for 24 hours with the speed of 50 rpm and in the entire study the temperature was maintained around $37\pm 0.5^{\circ}\text{C}$. The solution was kept aside for 6 hours for equilibrium. The solution was filtered through Whatman filter paper and the supernatant was analysed spectrophotometrically at 248 nm. The saturation solubility study data is noted in Table 21.

IR Analysis

The FTIR spectrum of rivaroxaban was recorded using Prestige-21 (SHIMADZU) with IR resolution software. The doing sample was placed in FTIR sample holder and scanned over the range of $400 - 4000\text{cm}^{-1}$. The spectrum obtained was shown in Figure 16 and structural assignments for the characteristic absorption bands were listed in Table 22.

7.1.1. Compatibility Studies

It is very important to perform physicochemical evaluation of all excipients which are probably used in the formulations. Interactions in the solid state between the active ingredient and excipients in pharmaceutical dosage forms can give rise to changes in the stability, solubility, dissolution rate and bioavailability for stable dosage forms. A compatibility study for rivaroxaban was carried out with potential formulation excipients to determine possibility of any drug-excipient interaction. Drug and excipients mixed in 1:1 ratio was stored at 40°C for 10 days. After 10 days the samples were analysed for chemical interaction by FTIR noted in Figure 17

7.2.1. Preliminary Trial Batches:

For preliminary study the tablet was formulated using HPMC E5, with SLS and without SLS. The formulated tablet was evaluated for drug release, the tablet shows variation in drug release as the concentration of SLS change from batch to batch. The composition and percent drug releases of preliminary batches are shown in Table 5, 6, and 7 respectively.

Table 5: Composition of Preliminary Batches

Ingredients (mg)	Batch No.			
	P1	P2	P3	P4
Rivaroxaban	20	20	20	20
HPMC E5	4.8	4.8	4.8	4.8
Sodium lauryl sulphate	-	0.4	-	0.4
MCC PH 101	88.2	87.8	88.2	87.8
Lactose Monohydrate	48	48	48	48
Cross Carmellose sodium	8	8	8	8
Magnesium stearate	1	1	1	1

Table 6: Preliminary Batches with % Drug Release

Dissolution Media without SLS	P1 Drug Release 67 % in 45 min	P2 Drug Release 81.7% in 45 min
Dissolution Media with SLS	P3 Drug Release 83 % in 45 min	P4 Drug Release 92% in 45 min

Table 7: In-vitro % Drug Release from Preliminary Batches

Time (min)	P1	P2	P3	P4
5	32.3±0.3	41.04±0.56	42.06±0.12	51.7±0.2
10	42.04±0.69	56.56±0.58	57.5±0.56	71.45±0.4
15	50.45±0.78	61.25±0.56	63.12±0.36	84.5±0.56
20	59.06±0.45	74.03±0.56	76.05±0.26	88.04±0.54
30	63.04±0.25	78.03±0.56	79.15±0.45	89.8±0.80
45	67.04±0.58	81.7±0.56	83.02±0.89	91.75±0.8

Figure 12: In-vitro % Drug Release from Preliminary Batches

7.2.2. Factorial Design

It is desirable to develop an acceptable pharmaceutical formulation in shortest possible time without wastage of raw materials. Traditionally pharmaceutical formulations after developed by changing one variable at a time approach. The method is time consuming in nature and requires a lot of imaginative efforts. Moreover, it may be difficult to evolve an ideal formulation using this classical technique since the joint effects of independent variables are not considered. It is therefore very essential to understand the complexity of pharmaceutical formulations by using established statistical tools such as factorial design. In addition to the art of formulation the technique of factorial design is an effective method of indicating the relative significance of a number of variables and their interaction the number of experiments required for

these studies is dependent on the number of independent variables selected. Factor is simply a categorical variable with 2 or more values, referred to as level. Factorial design in which 2 factor with three levels are present is called as 32 factorial designs. Factorial design is used to evaluate two or more factor simultaneously. A 32 full factorial design was constructed where HPMC and SLS were selected as factors and the level of 2 factors were selected on the basis of preliminary studies carried out before implementing the experimental design all the other formulations and processing variables were kept constant throughout the study. Two independent variables selected were HPMC E5 and SLS. As per experimental design nine formulations were formulated. From the in- vitro drug release of trial batch it was observed with the increase in SLS concentration % drug release also increased.

Table 8: Experimental Design Layout

Formulation		Coded Factor	
Code	Trial Code	X1	X2
F1	1	-1	-1
F2	2	0	0
F3	3	+1	+1
F4	4	0	-1
F5	5	-1	0
F6	6	0	+1
F7	7	+1	-1
F8	8	+1	0
F9	9	-1	+1

Composition of nine factorial batches is shown in Table 12.

Table 12: Formulation of Factorial Batches

Ingredient (mg)	Formulation Batches								
	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
Rivaroxaban	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20
MCC PH 101	88.6	87.4	86.2	87.6	88.4	87.2	86.6	86.4	88.2
Lactose Monohydrate	48	48	48	48	48	48	48	48	48
Cross Carmellose Sod.	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8
Hypromellose E5	3.8	4.8	5.8	4.8	3.8	4.8	5.8	5.8	3.8
Sodium Lauryl Sulphate	0.4	0.6	0.8	0.4	0.6	0.8	0.4	0.6	0.8
Magnesium Stearate	1.2	1.2	1.2	1.2	1.2	1.2	1.2	1.2	1.2
Total Weight	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170

Wet Granulation Process:

In the wet granulation process, granules were produced by using HPMC as a binder in water.

Subsequent drying and milling to produce granules³⁷. The steps used in wet granulation are mentioned as follows.

7.3 Evaluation of Immediate Release Tablet of Rivaroxaban Precompression Parameter:

A. Bulk Density:

Accurately weighed 10 gm sample of powder was placed into 25 ml measuring cylinder. Volume occupied by the powder was noted without disturbing the cylinder and the bulk density was calculated using the equation.³⁸

Bulk density = Weight of drug sample / Bulk volume

B. Tapped Density :(DT)

Accurately weighed 10 gm sample of powder was placed into 25 ml measuring cylinder. The cylinder was subjected to a fixed number of taps (~100), till there was no change in volume with further tapping. It is expressed in gm/10-3 L. The final volume was recorded and the tapped density was by the following equation:

Tapped density = Weight of drug sample / Tapped volume

C. Angle of Repose :(θ)

The angle of repose is indicative of flowability of the substance. Funnel was adjusted in such a way that the stem of the funnel lies 2.5 cm above the horizontal surface. The sample powder was allowed to flow from the funnel, so the height of the pile just touched the tip of the funnel. The diameter of the pile was determined by drawing a boundary along the circumference of the pile and taking the average of three diameters. The angle of repose is calculated by,

$$\tan \theta = h/r,$$

$$\theta = \tan^{-1} (h/r)$$

Where, θ = Angle of repose,

h = height of the pile in cm,

r = radius of the pile in cm

Relationship between Angle of Repose and Flow ability shown in Table 13.

Table 13: Flow Property of Powder

Flowability	Angle of Repose (θ)
Excellent	< 25
Good	25-30
Passable	30-40
Very poor	> 40

D. Carrs Index /Compressibility or Consolidation index:

The Carr's index is an indication of the compressibility of a powder. It was calculated by the formula,

$$CI = DT-DB/DT$$

Where, DT=Tapped density of powder, DB=Bulk density of powder, it is expressed in "Percentage".

E. Hausner's Ratio:

The Hausner's ratio is an indication of the compressibility of a powder. It is calculated by the formula,

$$\text{Hausner's ratio} = \text{Tapped density} / \text{Bulk density}$$

Compressibility and Hausner's ration shown in the Table 14:

Table 14: Compressibility Index and Hausner's Ratio

Compressibility index (%)	Flow character	Hausner's ratio
<10	Excellent	1.00-1.11
11-15	Good	1.12-1.18
16-20	Fair	1.19-1.25
21-25	Passable	1.26-1.34
26-31	Poor	1.35-1.45
32-38	Very poor	1.46-1.59
>39	Very, very poor	>1.60

Post Compression parameters

A. Physical Appearance

The general appearance of tablets includes the morphological characteristics like size, shape, colour, presence or absence of odour, surface texture etc.

B. Hardness Test

Monsanto hardness tester was used to check the hardness of the tablet. The tablet was placed vertically between the jaws of the tester. The two jaws placed under tension by spring and gauge. By turning the screw, the load was increased and at collapse the applied pressure from the spring was measured in kg/cm².

C. Thickness

The thickness of three randomly selected tablets from each formulation was determined in mm using a Digital Vernier Callipers. The observations are noted in Table 25

D. Friability test

The friability test is performed to evaluate the ability of tablets to withstand abrasion in packing, handling

and transporting. It is the phenomenon whereby tablet surfaces are damaged and show evidence of lamination or breakage when subjected to mechanical shock or attrition. The friability of tablet was determined by using friabilator as per USP procedure of friability. It is expressed in percentage (%). Twenty tablets were initially weighed (W1) and transferred into friabilator. The friabilator was operated at 25 rpm for 4 minutes or run up to 100 revolutions. The tablets were weighed again (W2). Friability of tablets less than 1% is considered acceptable. The percentage friability was then calculated by

$$\text{Friability} = \frac{W1 - W2}{W1} \times 100$$

Where, W1=Initial weight of tablet,
W2= Final weight

E. Uniformity of weight

To study weight variation, 20 tablets of each formulation were weighed using an electronic balance and the test was performed according to the official method. The % allowed difference in weight variation of tablets were analysed. Acceptance criteria is noted in Table 15.

Table 15: Acceptance criteria for tablet weight variation (USP 42-NF 37)

Average Weight of Tablet (mg)	% Difference Allowed
130 or less than	± 10
130-324	± 7.5
More than 324	± 5

F. Determination of Drug Content

The prepared formulations were analysed for drug content. Five immediate release tablets were weighed

and crushed to fine powder. An accurately weighed sample equivalent to 170 mg of the rivaroxaban was taken in a volumetric flask. The drug content was dissolved in 170 mg of pH 4.5 acetate buffer. This

solution was filtered through Whatman filter paper and respective dilution was done. The drug content was determined by measuring the absorbance at 248 nm using UV-spectrophotometer.

G. Disintegration test:

The test was carried out for 6 tablets using Tablet disintegration tester apparatus. Acetate buffer pH 4.5 at $37^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ was used as a disintegration media and the time in minutes taken for complete disintegration of the tablet with non-palpable mass remaining in the apparatus was measured.

H. In-vitro Drug Release Study

The in-vitro release of Rivaroxaban from immediate release tablet determined using a dissolution apparatus according to USP method II (paddle). This apparatus was placed in a water bath thermostated at $37 \pm 0.5^{\circ}\text{C}$ and stirred at a 75 rate of rpm. Sink conditions were maintained throughout the study. The dissolution medium was 900 ml of acetate buffer pH

4.5 with 0.4 % SLS and at regular time intervals 5 ml samples were withdrawn and replaced with fresh buffer solution. Samples were filtered and analysed using UV- spectrophotometer at 248 nm. Released drug contents were determined from the calibration curve^{39,40}. Dissolution profiles of all formulations were summarized in Table 26.

I. Kinetics of Drug Release

The Profile of all the formulations were fitted to first order kinetic to a certain the kinetic, first order kinetics, Higuchi, Hixson-Crowell. Korsmeyer and Peppas to a certain the kinetic modelling of the delivery by using DD solver and the model with the higher correlation coefficient was considered to be the best model the observations were summarised in Table 27. In order to know the drug release mechanism, the data was further analysed by Korsmeyer preposition and the value of n that is release exponent was calculated. The n value is future to interpret the release mechanism action in the Table 27.

Table 17: Interpretation of Diffusional Release Mechanism

Release Exponent(n)	Drug Transport Mechanism
0.5	Fickian diffusion
$0.5 < n < 1$	Anomalous transport
1.0	Case II transport
Higher than 1.0	Super Case II transport

J. Analysis of Data by Design Expert Software

A 32 full factorial design was selected and the 2 factors were evaluated at 3 levels, respectively Table 28. The statistical treatment and interpretation of data was done by State Ease Design Expert 13 software. The analysis of variance (ANOVA) is respected in Table 30. The data were subjected to 3-D response surface methodology to study the interaction of independent variables presented in Figure 19.

K. Grid Analysis

The grid analysis was performed for selection of the optimized level for Q30. The observations for Q30 were summarized in Table 30. The formulation F6 was selected as optimized formulation.

L. Comparison of Release Profile with Marketed Product

The in-vitro release studies were carried out for the marketed product (Xarelto, Bayer pharma Rivaroxaban 20 mg) in order to compare its release profile with optimized formulation of immediate release tablet of rivaroxaban.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The present study was undertaken to formulate a dosage form of poorly soluble drug by wet granulation method. The study involves preformulation studies of drug and excipients, formulation development and evaluation of dosage optimized formulation of immediate release tablet of rivaroxaban. The results and discussion of the above studies are as follows:

8.1. Preformulation Study

8.1.1. Identification of Rivaroxaban

8.1.1.1. Organoleptic Properties:

The procured drug sample was found to odourless, non-hygroscopic white to yellowish powder.

8.1.1.2. Melting Point:

Melting point of the drug was found to be 130°C which was in range of reported melting point 127°C-132°C.

8.1.1.3. Ultra violet (UV) Spectroscopy: (λ max determination)

The UV spectra of 10 ppm solution of rivaroxaban in acetate buffer showed absorption at wavelength 248 nm as per USP.

Spectrum of Rivaroxaban

Figure 13: Spectrum of Rivaroxaban

Calibration Curve of Rivaroxaban in 4.5 pH Acetate buffer:

Calibration curve of rivaroxaban in 4.5 pH acetate buffer shown as follows:

Table 18: Concentration and Absorbance of Rivaroxaban

Sr. no.	Concentration (ppm)	Absorbance ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)
1	2	0.06
2	4	0.12
3	6	0.14
4	8	0.2
5	10	0.27

Figure 14: Calibration Curve of Rivaroxaban in 4.5 pH Acetate buffer

Table 19: Parameters of Calibration Curve of Rivaroxaban in 4.5 pH Acetate buffer

Sr. No.	Parameter	Results
1	Absorption maxima (nm)	248 nm
2	Range $\mu\text{g/ml}$	2-10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$
3	Equation of calibration curve	$Y = 0.0256x + 0.0038$ 0.9847
4	Correlation coefficient(r^2)	

Figure 15: Calibration Curve of Rivaroxaban in 4.5 pH Acetate buffer with 0.4 % SLS**Table 20: Parameters of Calibration Curve of Rivaroxaban in 4.5 pH Acetate buffer with 0.4 % SLS**

Sr. No	Parameter	Results
1	Absorption maxima (nm)	247 nm
2	Range $\mu\text{g/ml}$	5-25 $\mu\text{g/ml}$
3	Equation of calibration curve	$Y = 0.0973x - 0.0081$
4	Correlation coefficient(r^2)	0.9946

8.1.1.4. IR Analysis:

Identification of rivaroxaban using IR spectroscopy. IR spectrum of rivaroxaban shown in Figure 5.

CONCLUSION:

Characteristic peak of functional group was observed in IR spectrum of rivaroxaban. The identification was confirmed and no impurity was detected in the spectrum of rivaroxaban. On the basis of melting point, UV spectrum, and FTIR spectrum the procured sample of rivaroxaban was found to be of acceptable

purity and quality. The sample was taken for further studies.

8.1.1.5. Saturation Solubility Studies

The solubility of rivaroxaban increased with increasing concentration of SLS. The solubility study performed with various solvents are shown in Table 22

Table 22: Solubility of Rivaroxaban in Different Solvents

Sr. no.	Solvent	Solubility (mg/ml)
1	0.1N HCl	0.0082
2	pH 6.8 phosphate buffer	0.015
3	pH4.5 acetate buffer	0.021
4	pH 4.5 acetate buffer with 0.4% SLS	0.08

8.1.1.6. Compatibility Study:

The successful formulation of a suitable and effective solid dosage form depends upon the careful selection of excipients. Excipients are added to facilitate administration, promote the consistent release and bioavailability of the drug. The thermal analysis and

FTIR Spectroscopy were used to investigate and predict any physiochemical interaction between component in a formulation and to the selection of suitable compatible excipients. FTIR Compatibility study of rivaroxaban and excipient mixture graph shown Figure 6:

Figure 17: FTIR Spectrum of Rivaroxaban and Excipients**Explanation:**

Overlay spectra of Rivaroxaban and all other excipient shown that characteristic peaks were slightly shifted but not more shifted from their wave number. The interaction was detected between rivaroxaban and all other excipients. There is a slight shifting of bond due to hydrogen bond or electrostatic bond. So, no significant interaction between

rivaroxaban and all excipients, hence it is compatible with each other.

8.2. Evaluation of Granules:

Many different types of angular properties have been employed to assist flowability, of these; Angle of repose is the most relevant. The value of angle of repose (θ) decreased after the addition of lubricant. The angle of repose was within the range of 23 $^{\circ}$ -30 $^{\circ}$

, indicative of good flowability. The bulk density of granules was found to be between 0.47 to 0.52 gm/cm³, the value indicates good packing capacity of granules. The tapped density of granules was found to

be 0.54 to 0.71 gm/cm³. The bulk density and tapped density was used to calculate the percent compressibility of the granules.

Table 24: Evaluation of Flow Properties of Blend

Formulation Code	Bulk Density	Tapped Density	Carr's Index	Hausner's Ratio	Angle of Repose
F1	0.523±0.30	0.66±0.42	16.80±0.98	1.30±0.32	23.24±0.23
F2	0.491±0.92	0.657±0.60	15.84±0.76	1.26±0.72	27.20±0.75
F3	0.478±0.34	0.549±0.20	18.25±0.54	1.23±0.06	30.45±0.42
F4	0.481±0.64	0.652±0.60	17.87±0.84	1.25±0.45	26.07±0.60
F5	0.494±0.30	0.697±0.35	14.72±0.46	1.29±0.42	30.62±0.78
F6	0.485±0.74	0.712±0.26	19.15±0.34	1.22±0.37	23.96±0.88
F7	0.502±0.23	0.674±0.42	15.06±0.75	1.21±0.23	29.17±0.56
F8	0.515±0.24	0.680±0.23	18.34±0.23	1.24±0.44	26.76±0.42
F9	0.479±0.06	0.658±0.54	17.29±0.36	1.22±0.35	28.56±0.27

n=3 All values expressed as mean ± SD

Evaluation of Immediate release tablet/ Evaluation of Factorial Formulations:

All formulated tablets were smooth and circular with good texture. The thickness of the tablet was found to

be between 2.80 to 3.00 mm, due to constant tablet press setting irrespective of weight variation. The hardness of the tablet was found to be in the range of 4 to 6.0 kg/cm². This ensured good mechanical strength. The drug content of the tablet was found to be in the range of 91.12 to 95.02%. Observations are Summarised in the Table [24]

Table 25: Evaluation Parameters of Immediate Release Tablet of Rivaroxaban

Formulation Code	Hardness (kg/cm ²)	Thickness (mm)	Average Weight (mg)	Friability (%)	Drug Content (%)	Disintegration Time (sec)
F1	4.8± 0.2	2.80±0.05	173.3±0.72	0.79±0.01	91.89±0.61	70-81
F2	4.2± 0.6	2.83±0.06	170.7±0.46	0.67±0.01	93.11±0.42	118-140
F3	4.3± 0.6	2.87±0.04	170.3±0.32	0.57±0.01	91.12±0.71	120-134
F4	5.7± 0.8	2.86±0.06	172.1±0.54	0.55±0.00	91.45±0.63	90-100
F5	5.4± 0.3	2.87±0.06	171.6±0.32	0.51±0.01	92.57±0.42	60-72
F6	5.0± 0.2	2.90±0.05	170.1±0.65	0.67±0.03	95.02±0.32	88-94
F7	5.9± 0.4	2.97±0.06	169.7±0.24	0.52±0.87	92.83±0.43	125-131
F8	5.7± 0.6	2.97±0.02	170.1±0.45	0.56±0.67	93.36±0.61	132-140
F9	5.4± 0.3	3.00±0.06	172.8±0.64	0.40±0.04	93.24±0.44	97-104

n=3 All values are expressed as mean ± SD

8.3. In-vitro Drug Release of Factorial Batches

Prepared tablets were subjected to in vitro drug release studies in pH 4.5 Acetate buffer with 0.4%

SLS for 45 min. The dissolution profile of all formulations was summarized in Table [26]. The formulation F6 meets USP Dissolution test acceptance criteria.

Table 26: In-vitro Drug Release of Factorial Batches

F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
47.19±0. 3	46.64±0. 7	47.03±0. 52	45.9±0.4 1	44.89±0. 53	49.41±0. 42	46.94±0.5 5	43.84±0. 51	48.01±0. 54
68.82±0. 41	72.17±0. 51	70.98±0. 55	71.62±0. 36	69.92±0. 47	72.94±0. 33	70.95±0.6 1	71.53±0. 46	69.98±0. 52
82.12±0. 6	84.78±0. 45	83.32±0. 61	85.12±0. 43	84.67±0. 61	86.04±0. 51	84.76±0.7 5	85.23±0. 62	85.12±0. 55
86.68±0. 32	88.38±0. 71	87.32±0. 48	87.67±0. 74	88.04±0. 56	90.13±0. 64	86.78±0.4 6	89.06±0. 43	88.34±0. 36
90.22±0. 53	91.02±0. 63	89.74±0. 36	89.99±0. 44	90.97±0. 6	93.21±0. 46	91.88±0.5 3	92.19±0. 48	91.23±0. 61
91.89±0. 61	93.11±0. 42	91.12±0. 71	91.45±0. 63	92.57±0. 42	95.02±0. 32	92.83±0.4 3	93.36±0. 61	93.24±0. 44

n=3 All values are expressed as mean ± SD

Figure 18: % Drug Release of Factorial Batches

8.4. Mathematical Modeling of Release Kinetics

Various mathematical models for predicting the drug release by dissolution profile of all the formulated batches i.e., Korsmeyer-Peppas, zero order, first order, Hixon Crowell, Higuchi release model to ascertain the kinetic modelling of drug release by using DD Solver software. Coefficient of determination (R) and release constant (k) for each dissolution model were evaluated. Large value of R indicates that profile fits best to the model.

Analysis of Data by Design Expert Software

Traditional designing of the pharmaceutical formulations is based on time consuming approach of changing one variable at time which does not take into consideration the joint effect of independent

variables. Thus, factorial design can serve as an essential tool to understand the complexity of the pharmaceutical formulations. The results can be expressed either as simple linear or second order polynomial equation to statistically evaluate the responses obtained after experiments. The 3^o full factorial design was selected to study the effect of independent variables HPMC E5 (X1) and SLS (X2) on dependent variable Q30. A statistical model incorporating interactive and polynomial terms was utilized to evaluate the responses.

$$Y = b_0 + b_1 X_1 + b_2 X_2 + b_{12} X_1 X_2 + b_{11} X_1^2 + b_{22} X_2^2$$

Where, Y is the dependent variable, b₀ is the arithmetic mean response of the nine runs and b_i (b₁, b₂, b₁₂, b₁₁ and b₂₂) is the estimated coefficient for

the corresponding factor Xi (X1, X2, X12, X11, and X22), which represents the average results of changing one factor at a time from its low to high value. The interaction term (X1, X2) depicts the changes in the response when two factors are simultaneously changed. The polynomial terms (X12 and X 2 are included to investigate nonlinearity. The Q30 for the nine formulations of design showed variation, the responses of the formulations prepared by 32 factorial designs were indicated in Table 29. The data clearly indicate that Q30 values are strongly dependent on the selected independent variables. The fitted regression equations relating the responses Q30 are shown in the following equations,

$$Q30 = 90.08 - 3.31 * X1 + 2.48 * X2 - 0.4075 * X1 * X2 - 2.58 * X1 * X1 - 0.3667 * X2 * X2$$

Final equations in Terms of Actual Factors:

$$Q30 = 90.08 - 3.31 * HPMC + 2.48 * SLS - 0.4075 * HPMC * SLS - 2.58 * HPMC^2 - 0.3667 * SLS^2$$

The information the equation conveyed was the basis to study effects of variables. The regression coefficient values are the estimates of the model fitting. The r2 was high indicating the adequate fitting of the quadratic model. The response data was analysed by using State Ease design expert version 13 software. The software gives statistical analysis of data. The summary of statistical design and summary of response are reported in Table 28 and 29.

Final Equations in Terms of Coded Factors:

Table 28: Summary of Statistical Design

Factor	Name	Units	Type	Actual values		Coded values	
				Low	High	Low	High
A	HPMC E5	mg	Numeric	3.8	5.8	-1	+1
B	Sodium lauryl	mg	Numeric	0.4	0.8	-1	+1

Table 29: Summary of Response

Response	Name	Units	Obs.	Analysis	Min.	Max.	Mean
Y1	Drug Release	%	9	Polynomial	91.12	95.02	93.07

Figure 19: Response Surface Plot for % Drug Release

Where, MAS= % Drug Release in 30 min

8.6. Grid Analysis

Grid analysis was performed for selection of optimized level for Q30. The formulation F6 was selected as optimized formulation.

Table 31: Search for Optimized Level for Q30

	-1	-0.8	-0.6	-0.4	-0.2	0	0.2	0.4	0.6	0.8	1
-1	87.55	87.90	88.04	87.98	87.23	87.23	86.54	85.65	84.56	83.26	81.75
-0.8	88.26	88.59	88.72	88.64	88.35	87.86	87.16	86.25	85.14	83.82	82.29
-0.6	88.94	89.26	89.37	89.27	88.96	88.45	87.74	86.82	85.69	84.35	82.81
-0.4	89.59	89.89	89.98	89.87	89.55	89.02	88.29	87.35	86.21	84.86	83.30
-0.2	90.21	90.50	90.57	90.44	89.56	89.56	88.82	87.86	86.70	85.33	83.76
0	90.81	91.07	91.13	90.99	90.63	90.08	89.31	88.34	87.16	85.78	84.19
0.2	91.37	91.62	91.66	91.50	91.13	90.56	89.77	88.79	87.59	86.19	84.58
0.4	91.90	92.14	92.16	91.98	91.60	91.01	90.21	89.21	88.00	86.58	84.96
0.6	92.41	92.62	92.63	92.44	92.04	91.43	90.62	89.60	88.37	86.94	85.30
0.8	92.88	93.08	93.08	92.87	92.45	91.82	90.99	89.96	88.71	87.26	85.61
1	91.33	93.51	93.49	93.26	92.83	92.19	91.34	90.29	89.03	87.56	87.65

8.7. Comparison of Release Profile with Marketed Preparation

The release profile of the F6 were compared with that of marketed preparation (Xarelto). The observed F2 (Differential Factor) value is 74.457.

Table 32: Comparison of Release Profile with Marketed Preparations

Time (min)	Drug Release (%)	
	Xarelto 20 mg	F6
5	45.21	49.41
10	68.41	72.94
15	85.49	86.04
20	88.52	90.13
30	90.34	93.21
45	92.23	95.02

Figure 20: Comparison of Release Profile with Marketed Preparations

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

The majority of drugs are provided in oral dose forms. Oral administration of conventional or immediate release preparations, as well as some modified release

preparations, results in a wide range of bioavailability. A variety of factors impact bioavailability, including posture, gender, age, illness status, fed or fasted state, volume of food consumed, stomach emptying, and the absorption window of the drug in a specific area of the

gastro-intestinal tract. To ensure patient compliance, recent advances in patient-oriented dose form have emerged. Immediate release tablets are intended to breakdown and release drug without the need of any particular rate-controlling characteristics. Immediate release dosage forms in which $\geq 85\%$ of the indicated quantity dissolves in 30 minutes or less. The aim of this study was to develop generic rivaroxaban immediate release tablets employing rivaroxaban modification 1. The study is divided into many steps, the first of which is the procurement of API, followed by the use of the procured sample in formulation development, i.e., preliminary trial batches and factorial design. The third step is to evaluate the immediate release tablet, which includes pre-compressional characteristics such as flow properties as well as post-compressional characteristics such as hardness, thickness, friability, weight variation, disintegration test, in-vitro drug release, and kinetic studies. The following step is to optimise all of the factorial batches using statistical data analysis and grid analysis using State ease design expert 13 software. The developed formulation F6 was found to be an optimised formulation. The optimised formulation is then compared to marketed preparation (Xarelto). Rivaroxaban is an anticoagulant and the first orally active direct factor Xa inhibitor. It is indicated for the prevention of venous thromboembolic events. It belongs to BCS Class-II having low solubility and high permeability. The immediate release tablet formulated using super disintegrants and a surfactant improves the disintegration and dissolution of rivaroxaban tablet. The study reveals successful application of factorial design and optimization technique for the development of immediate release tablet of rivaroxaban. gciyguo

The investigation carried out so far has encouraged for drawing the following conclusion:

- A 3^2 full factorial was performed and the desired release of rivaroxaban from tablet was achieved through careful monitoring of the selected formulation variables.
 - The statistical approach for formulation optimization is useful tool.
 - The variable % drug release evaluated in the study exhibited significant effect on the response Q30
- of the formulation. It was evident that increase in concentration of HPMC slightly decreases the drug release and increase in the concentration of SLS increases the % drug release.
- The Grid analysis was performed for the selection of optimized level for release profile Q30 revealed F6 as the optimized formulation.
 - The best results for Q30 were obtained at the upper-level concentration of SLS and middle level concentration of HPMC which revealed the release profile Q30 as per the USP acceptance criteria.
 - The comparative study of marketed formulation and optimized formulation revealed that Xarelto (20 mg) has 92 % drug release and F6 has 95 % drug release in 45 min. Thus, F6 is superior than the marketed Xarelto.
 - The optimized formulation (F6) leads to the development of immediate release tablet of rivaroxaban using the 3^2 full factorial design.

Finally, it is concluded that release of rivaroxaban is immediate and thus it is promising approach for the treatment of venous thromboembolic events.

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